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On Annihilator Fuzzy Ideals 2

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ABSTRACT

In 1965, (Zadeh L.A.) introduced the concept of fuzzy subset. Since that time many papers were introduced in different mathematical scopes of theoretical and practical applications.

In 1982, (Liu W.J.) formulated the term of fuzzy ring and fuzzy ideal of a ring R . In 2000 (Hameed A.T) introduced the concept of Annihilator fuzzy Ideals and gives some properties of it .

The main aim of this paper is give several basic properties about this concept .

S . 1 BASIC CONCEPT:

This section contains some definitions and properties of fuzzy subset, fuzzy ring, fuzzy ideal which we will be used in the next section .

PRELIMINARY CONCEPTS

Let R be a subset . A **fuzzy subset of R** is a function from R into $[0,1], ([1], [2])$.

Let A and B be fuzzy subset of R . We write $A \subseteq B$ if $A(x) \leq B(x)$ for all $x \in R$. If $A \subseteq B$ and there exists $x \in R$ such that $A(x) < B(x)$, then we write $A \subset B$ and we say that A is a proper fuzzy subset of B , [1]. Note that $A = B$ if and only if $A(x) = B(x)$, for all $x \in R$, [3].

We let $\text{Im}(A)$ denote **the image of A** . We say that A is a finite – valued if $\text{Im}(A)$ is finite , ([1],[4])| $|\text{Im}(A)|$ denote **the cardinality of $\text{Im}(A)$** , [4] .

For each $t \in [0,1]$, the set $A_t = \{ x \in R \mid A(x) \geq t \}$ is called **a level subset of R** and the set $A^* = \{ x \in R \mid A(x) = A(0) \}$, ([1], [4]).

The set $\text{supp } A = \{ x \in R \mid A(x) > 0 \}$ and the set $A_{\#} = \{ x \in R \mid A(x) > A(1) \}$, ([1], [4]).

Let $x \in R$ and $t \in [0,1]$, let x_t denote the fuzzy subset of R defined by $x_t(y) = 0$ if $x \neq y$ and $x_t(y) = t$ if $x = y$ for all $y \in R$. x_t is called a **fuzzy singleton of R** , [4] .

If x_t and y_s are fuzzy singletons, then $x_t + y_s = (x + y)_\lambda$ and $x_t \circ y_s = (x y)_\lambda$ where $\lambda = \min \{ t, s \}$, ([3],[4]).

Let $I^R = \{A_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a collection of fuzzy subsets of R . Define the fuzzy subset of R (**intersection**) by $(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} A_i)(x) = \inf \{ A_i(x) \mid i \in \Lambda \}$ for all $x \in R$,([2],[4]).

Let \emptyset denote $\emptyset(x) = 0$ for all $x \in R$, **the empty fuzzy subset** of R ,([3],[5]). Note that throughout our work any fuzzy subset is a nonempty fuzzy subset.

Let A and B be a fuzzy subsets of R , **the product $A \circ B$** define by :

$$A \circ B(x) = \sup \{ \min \{ A(y), B(z) \} \mid x = yz \} \quad y, z \in R, \text{ for all } x \in R.$$

The addition $A + B$ define by : $(A + B)(x) = \sup \{ \min \{ A(y), B(z) \} \mid x = y + z \} \quad y, z \in R$, for all $x \in R$, [5] .

Let A be a fuzzy subset of R , A is called a **fuzzy subgroup** of a group R if for all $x, y \in R$, $A(x + y) \geq \min \{ A(x), A(y) \}$ and $A(x) = A(-x)$, [5] .

Let A be a fuzzy subset of R , A is called a **fuzzy ring of a ring R** if for all $x, y \in R$, $A(x - y) \geq \min \{ A(x), A(y) \}$ and $A(xy) \geq \min \{ A(x), A(y) \}$ ([1],[5]).

In this paper, $(R, +, \cdot)$ be a commutative ring with identity.

Now, we give definition and some properties of fuzzy ideal .

DEFINITION 1.1 [1],[5]:

A fuzzy subset A of R is called a **fuzzy ideal of R** if and only if for all $x, y \in R$, $A(x - y) \geq \min \{ A(x), A(y) \}$ and $A(xy) \geq \max \{ A(x), A(y) \}$.

REMARK 1.1 [6]:

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R and A be a fuzzy ideal of R such that $A \subseteq X$. Then A is a **fuzzy ideal of the fuzzy ring X** .

DEFINITION 1.2 [6],[7]:

A is called a **fuzzy ideal of the fuzzy ring X** of R , if $A(b-c) \geq \min \{ A(b), A(c) \}$ and $A(bc) \geq \min \{ \max \{ A(b), A(c) \}, X(bc) \}$.

PROPOSITION 1.1 [1][4][7]:

Let A be a fuzzy ideal of R . If for all $t \in [0, A(0)]$, then A_t is an ideal of R , A^* is an ideal of R , $A_\#$ is an ideal of R and $\text{supp } A$ is an ideal of R .

PROPOSITION 1.2 [8] :

Let $\{A_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy ideals of R. Then $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} A_i$ is a fuzzy ideal of R .

ROPOSITION 1.3 [8], [9] :

Let A and B are fuzzy ideals of R, then $A + B$ is fuzzy ideal of R.

Moreover, if $A(0) = B(0)$, then $A, B \subseteq A + B$. Also $A + A = A$.

LEMMA 1.1 :

If a ,b and $c \in [0,1]$,then :

- 1) $\max \{a , \min \{b ,c\}\} \leq \sup \{a ,b ,c \}$.
- 2) $\max \{a , \min \{b ,c\}\} \geq \inf \{a ,b ,c \}$.

Proof :

Since a ,b and $c \in [0,1]$,

- 1) If $a \leq b \leq c$,then $\max \{a , \min \{b ,c\}\} = \max \{a ,b \} = b$.
 $\sup \{a ,b ,c \} = c$, $\inf \{a ,b ,c \} = a$.
- 2) If $a \leq c \leq b$,then $\max \{a , \min \{b ,c\}\} = \max \{a ,c \} = c$.
 $\sup \{a ,b ,c \} = b$, $\inf \{a ,b ,c \} = a$.
- 3) If $b \leq a \leq c$,then $\max \{a , \min \{b ,c\}\} = \max \{a ,b \} = a$.
 $\sup \{a ,b ,c \} = c$, $\inf \{a ,b ,c \} = b$.
- 4) If $c \leq a \leq b$,then $\max \{a , \min \{b ,c\}\} = \max \{a ,c \} = a$.
 $\sup \{a ,b ,c \} = b$, $\inf \{a ,b ,c \} = c$.
- 5) If $b \leq c \leq a$,then $\max \{a , \min \{b ,c\}\} = \max \{a ,b \} = a$.
 $\sup \{a ,b ,c \} = a$, $\inf \{a ,b ,c \} = b$.
- 6) If $c \leq b \leq a$, then $\max \{a , \min \{b ,c\}\} = \max \{a ,c \} = a$.
 $\sup \{a ,b ,c \} = a$, $\inf \{a ,b ,c \} = c$.

Hence $\max \{a , \min \{b ,c\}\} \leq \sup \{a ,b ,c \}$ and $\max \{a , \min \{b ,c\}\} \geq \inf \{a ,b ,c \}$.

PROPOSITION 1.4 :

Let A and B are fuzzy ideals of R , then $A \circ B$ is a fuzzy ideal of R .

Proof :

$$\begin{aligned} (A \circ B)(0) &= \sup \{ \min \{A(a),B(b)\} \mid 0=ab \}, a ,b \in R. \\ &= \sup \{ \min \{A(0),B(0)\}, \dots \} > 0, \end{aligned}$$

then $(A \circ B)$ is a nonempty fuzzy subset of R .

Let $x, y \in R$ such that $x=ab$ and $y=cd$, $a ,b ,c ,d \in R$,then $x-y=ab-cd$.

$$x-y = ab-cd = ab - cd + ad - ad = a(b-d) + d(a-c).$$

$$(A \circ B)(x-y) = \sup \{ \min \{ A(p), B(q) \} \mid x-y=pq \}, p, q \in R.$$

$$= \sup \{ \min \{ A(a(b-d)), B(d(a-c)) \} \mid x-y=ab-cd \}.$$

$$\geq \sup \{ \min \{ \max \{ A(a), A(b-d) \}, \max \{ B(d), B(a-c) \} \} \mid x-y=ab-cd \},$$

(A and B are fuzzy ideals).

$$\geq \sup \{ \min \{ \max \{ A(a), \min \{ A(b), A(d) \} \}, \max \{ B(d), \min \{ B(a), B(c) \} \} \} \mid x-y=ab-cd \},$$

(A and B are fuzzy ideals).

$$\geq \sup \{ \min \{ \inf \{ A(a), A(b), A(d) \}, \inf \{ B(d), B(a), B(c) \} \} \mid x-y=ab-cd \}, \text{ (by lemma (1.1)).}$$

$$\geq \min \{ \sup \{ \min \{ A(a), B(d) \} \}, \sup \{ \min \{ A(b), B(a) \} \}, \sup \{ \min \{ A(d), B(c) \} \} \mid x-y=ab-cd \},$$

by[10].

$$\geq \min \{ \sup \{ \min \{ A(a), B(d) \} \}, \sup \{ \min \{ A(d), B(c) \} \} \mid x=ab, y=cd \}.$$

$$= \min \{ (A \circ B)(x), (A \circ B)(y) \}.$$

$$(A \circ B)(x-y) = \min \{ (A \circ B)(x), (A \circ B)(y) \} \dots(1).$$

$$(A \circ B)(xy) = (A \circ B)(ab-cd) \geq (A \circ B)(ab) = (A \circ B)(x).$$

$$(A \circ B)(xy) = (A \circ B)(ab-cd) \geq (A \circ B)(cd) = (A \circ B)(y).$$

$$(A \circ B)(xy) \geq \max \{ (A \circ B)(x), (A \circ B)(y) \} \dots(2).$$

Hence by (1) and (2), $A \circ B$ is a fuzzy ideal of R .

S.2 THE ANNIHILATOR OF A FUZZY IDEAL :

In this section, we give the concept of Annihilator of a fuzzy ideal of a ring R and we give some examples and properties about Annihilator of fuzzy ideal of R .

DEFINITION 2.1 [9]:

Let A be a nonempty fuzzy ideal of R . The Annihilator of A denoted by $(F\text{-Ann } A)$ is defined by $\{ x_t : x \in R, x_t \circ A \subseteq \theta_1 \}, t \in [0, A(0)]$.

Note that $(F\text{-Ann } A)(a) = \sup \{ t : t \in [0, A(0)], a_t \circ A \subseteq \theta_1 \}, a \in R$.

EXAMPLE 2.1 [9]:

1. The fuzzy ring $A(x)=1$ for all $x \in Z$ is a fuzzy ideal of Z .

$$F\text{-Ann } A = \{ x_t : x \in Z, x_t \circ A \subseteq \theta_1 \}, t \in [0, A(0)].$$

$$\text{For any } a \in Z, (F\text{-Ann } A)(a) = \sup \{ t : t \in [0, A(0)], a_t \circ A \subseteq \theta_1 \}.$$

$$\text{Let } x \in R, (a_t \circ A)(x) = \sup \{ \min \{ a_t(y), A(z) \} \mid x=y, z \}, y, z \in R.$$

$$(a_t \circ A)(0) = t \text{ for all } a \in Z.$$

$$\text{Let } n \in Z, n \neq 0 \text{ (} n=n.1 \text{ or } n=1.n \text{)}.$$

$$(\theta_t \circ A)(n) = \sup \{ \min \{0,1\}, \min \{0,1\} \} = 0 \Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann } A)(0) = 1.$$

$$(I_t \circ A)(1) = \sup \{ \min \{t,1\}, \min \{0,1\} \} = t \Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann } A)(1) = 0.$$

$$(2_t \circ A)(n) = \sup \{ \min \{t,1\}, \min \{0,1\} \} = t \Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann } A)(2) = 0.$$

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$$(m_t \circ A)(n) = \sup \{ \min \{0,1\}, \min \{0,1\} \} = 0 \text{ if } n \neq m.$$

$$(m_t \circ A)(n) = \sup \{ \min \{t,1\}, \min \{0,1\} \} = t \text{ if } n = m.$$

$$\Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann } A)(m) = 0.$$

Hence :

$$(F\text{-Ann } A)(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2. Let A be a fuzzy ideal of Z_2 such that :

$$A(x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x = 1 \end{cases}$$

where $c \in (0,1]$.

$$(\theta_t \circ A)(0) = t, (\theta_t \circ A)(1) = 0 \Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann } A)(0) = c.$$

$$(I_t \circ A)(0) = t, (I_t \circ A)(1) = 0 \Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann } A)(1) = c.$$

Hence $(F\text{-Ann } A)(x) = c$ for all $x \in Z_2$.

PROPOSITION 2.1 [9]:

The Annihilator of a fuzzy ideal A of R ($F\text{-Ann } A$) is a fuzzy ideal of R.

PROPOSITION 2.2 [9]:

Let A be a fuzzy ideal of R. Then $A \subseteq F\text{-Ann } \text{Ann } A$.

PROPOSITION 2.3 [9]:

Let A and B be two fuzzy ideals of R such that $A(0) = B(0)$. Then :

$$(F\text{-Ann } A) \cap (F\text{-Ann } B) = F\text{-Ann } (A+B).$$

PROPOSITION 2.4 [9]:

Let A and B be two fuzzy ideals of R. Then :

$$(F\text{-Ann } A) + (F\text{-Ann } B) \subseteq F\text{-Ann } (A \cap B).$$

PROPOSITION 2.5 :

Let $\{A_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy ideals of R. Then $\sum_{i \in \Lambda} F - Ann(A_i) \subseteq F - Ann \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} A_i$

for all A_i fuzzy ideal of R $i = 1, 2, \dots$

Proof:

Since $(F - Ann A_1) + (F - Ann A_2) \subseteq F - Ann (A_1 \cap A_2)$, proposition (2.).

Now, $(F - Ann A_1) + (F - Ann A_2) + (F - Ann A_3) \subseteq F - Ann (A_1 \cap A_2) + (F - Ann A_3)$.

$$= F - Ann (B_1) + (F - Ann A_3) \text{ where } B_1 = A_1 \cap A_2.$$

$$\subseteq F - Ann (B_1 \cap A_3) \text{ where } B_1 = A_1 \cap A_2.$$

$$= F - Ann (A_1 \cap A_2 \cap A_3).$$

To prove that $\sum_{i \in \Lambda} F - Ann(A_i) \subseteq F - Ann \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} A_i$ for all A_i .

$$(F - Ann A_1) + (F - Ann A_2) + \dots + (F - Ann A_n) \subseteq F - Ann (A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_n).$$

$$\subseteq (F - Ann B_1) + (F - Ann A_3) + \dots + (F - Ann A_n), \text{ where } B_1 = A_1 \cap A_2.$$

$$\subseteq (F - Ann B_2) + (F - Ann A_4) + \dots + (F - Ann A_n), \text{ where } B_2 = A_1 \cap A_2 \cap A_3.$$

$$\subseteq (F - Ann B_3) + (F - Ann A_5) + \dots + (F - Ann A_n), \text{ where } B_3 = A_1 \cap A_2 \cap A_3 \cap A_4.$$

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$$\subseteq (F - Ann B_{n-2}) + (F - Ann A_n), \text{ where } B_{n-2} = A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_{n-1}.$$

$$\subseteq (F - Ann B_{n-1}), \text{ where } B_{n-1} = A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_n.$$

$$= F - Ann(A_1 \cap A_2 \cap \dots \cap A_n).$$

REMARK 2.1 :

The converse of proposition(2.14) is not true as the following example shows .

EXAMPLE 2.2 :

Converse the ring $R = Z_{12}$. Let A and B : $R \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that :

$$A(x) = \begin{cases} 1/4 & \text{if } x \in \langle 2 \rangle \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

and

$$B(x) = \begin{cases} 1/8 & \text{if } x \in \langle 3 \rangle \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

It is clear A and B are fuzzy ideals of R .

$$(A \cap B)(x) = \begin{cases} 1/8 & \text{if } x \in \langle 6 \rangle \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

and $F\text{-Ann}(A \cap B)(x) = 1/8$ for all $x \in \langle 2 \rangle$. But

$$(F\text{-Ann}A)(x) = \begin{cases} 1/4 & \text{if } x \in \langle 6 \rangle \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

and

$$(F\text{-Ann}B)(x) = \begin{cases} 1/8 & \text{if } x \in \langle 4 \rangle \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Thus } [(F\text{-Ann}A) + (F\text{-Ann}B)](f) = \begin{cases} 1/8 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

, implies that $F\text{-Ann}(A \cap B) \not\subseteq (F\text{-Ann}A) + (F\text{-Ann}B)$.

PROPOSITION 2.6 [9] :

Let A be a fuzzy ideal of R , then $\text{Im}(F\text{-Ann}A) \subseteq \{0, A(0)\}$. That is $(\text{Im}(F\text{-Ann}A) | \leq 2)$.

PROPOSITION 2.7 :

Let X be fuzzy ring of R and $a \in R$, $[F\text{-Ann}(a_t)]_k = \text{ann}(a)$ for all $t, k \in (0, X(0))$.

Proof :

$$\text{Let } x \in [F\text{-Ann}(a_t)]_k \Leftrightarrow x_k \subseteq F\text{-Ann}(a_t)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow x_k a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow x a = 0$$

$$\Leftrightarrow x \in \text{ann}(a).$$

PROPOSITION 2.8 :

Let X be a fuzzy ring of R and $a \in R, t \in [0, X(0)]$, then :

$F\text{-Ann}(a_t)$ is a fuzzy ideal of a fuzzy ring X of a ring R , when $F\text{-Ann}(a_t) \subseteq X$.

Proof :

Let $b, c \in R$, to prove the following :

- 1- $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b-c) \geq \min \{ F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b), F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(c) \}$.
- 2- $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(bc) \geq \min \{ \max \{ F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b), F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(c) \}, X(bc) \}$.

Now, let $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b) = h$ and $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(c) = k$, where $h, k \in (0, X(0))$.

Let $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b-c) = r$, to prove $r \geq \min \{ h, k \} = \lambda$.

Since $b_h a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$ and $c_k a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$ and $b_\lambda \subseteq b_h, c_\lambda \subseteq c_k$, then $b_\lambda a_t \subseteq b_h a_t, c_\lambda a_t \subseteq c_k a_t$, [9], implies that $b_\lambda a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}, c_\lambda a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$, [9].

Hence $(b_\lambda a_t) - (c_\lambda a_t) \subseteq 0_{X(0)} - 0_{X(0)} = 0_{X(0)}$, [9], implies that $(b_\lambda - c_\lambda) a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$ and $(b - c)_\lambda a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$. Then $(b - c)_\lambda \subseteq F\text{-Ann}(a_t)$.

But $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b-c) = \sup \{ \beta : \beta \in (0, X(0)), (b-c)_\beta a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)} \} = r \geq \lambda$.

The first condition is true.

Now, to prove the second condition. Let $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(bc) = r$ and $X(bc) = q$.

To prove $r \geq \min \{ \max \{ h, k \}, q \}$. Suppose that $\max \{ h, k \} = h$, $(bc)_r a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)}$

But $(bc)_h a_t \subseteq ((bc)_\gamma a_t) \subseteq (c(ba))_\gamma \subseteq (c_h(b_h a_t)) \subseteq c_h 0_{X(0)} = 0_{X(0)}$ where $\gamma = \min \{ h, t \}$.

Since $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(bc) = \sup \{ \beta : \beta \in (0, X(0)), (bc)_\beta a_t \subseteq 0_{X(0)} \} = r \geq h$.

Similarly, if $\max \{ h, k \} = k$, then $r \geq k$.

Hence $r \geq \max \{ h, k \}$, then $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)$ is a fuzzy ideal of R .

Since $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(bc) \subseteq X(bc)$, then $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(bc) \geq \min \{ \max \{ F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(b), F\text{-Ann}(a_t)(c) \}, X(bc) \}$.

Thus $F\text{-Ann}(a_t)$ is a fuzzy ideal of a fuzzy ring X of a ring R .

S.3 THE ANNIHILATOR FUZZY IDEAL :

In this section, we give the concept of Annihilator fuzzy ideal of a ring R and we give some examples and properties of this concept.

DEFINITION 3.1 [9] :

Let A be a nonempty fuzzy ideal of a ring R . A is called an Annihilator fuzzy ideal if and only if $A = F\text{-Ann Ann } A$.

EXAMPLE 3.1 [9] :

1. The fuzzy ring $A(x) = 1$ for all $x \in Z$ is a fuzzy ideal of Z .

By example (2.1, 1), $(F\text{-Ann } A)(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Let $F\text{-Ann } A = B$. It is clear that $B(0) = A(0) = 1$.

Note that: $F\text{-Ann } B = \{ x_t : x \in Z, x_t \circ B \subseteq 0_1 \}, t \in [0, B(0)]$.

For any $a \in Z$, $(F\text{-Ann } B)(a) = \sup \{ t : t \in [0, B(0)], a_t \circ B \subseteq 0_1 \}$.

Let $b \in Z$, $(a_t \circ B)(x) = \sup \{ \min \{ a_t(c), B(d) \} \mid b = cd \}, c, d \in Z$.

$(a_t \circ B)(0) = t$ for all $a \in Z$, let $n \in Z, n \neq 0$ ($n = n.1$ or $n = 1.n$).

$$(0_t \circ B)(n) = \sup \{ \min \{0,0\}, \min \{0,0\} \} = 0 \Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann } B)(0) = 1.$$

$$(I_t \circ B)(n) = \sup \{ \min \{0,0\}, \min \{t,0\} \} = 0 \Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann } B)(1) = 1.$$

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$$(m_t \circ B)(n) = \sup \{ \min \{t,0\}, \min \{0,0\} \} = 0, \text{ if } n=m.$$

$$(m_t \circ B)(n) = \sup \{ \min \{0,0\}, \min \{0,0\} \} = 0, \text{ if } n \neq m.$$

$\Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann } B)(m) = 1$ for all $m \in Z$. Thus $F\text{-Ann } B = A$.

Hence A is an Annihilator fuzzy ideal of Z .

2. Let A be a fuzzy ideal of Z_2 such that :

$$A(x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{where } c \in (0,1).$$

By example (2.1, 2), $(F\text{-Ann } A)(x) = c$ for all $x \in Z_2$ and by similar argument of [9,2.2.2, (4)]

$$(F\text{-AnnAnn}A)(x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Hence A is an Annihilator fuzzy ideal of Z_2 .

PROPOSITION 3.1 [9] :

Let A be an Annihilator fuzzy ideal of R , then $|\text{Im}(A)| \leq 2$. That is $\text{Im}(A) \subseteq \{0, A(0)\}$.

PROPOSITION 3.2 [9] :

Let A be an Annihilator fuzzy ideal of R . Then:

A_t is an annihilator ideal of R for all $t \in [0, A(0)]$.

PROPOSITION 3.3 :

Let A be an Annihilator fuzzy ideal of R . Then:

- 1) A^* is an annihilator ideal of R and $(F\text{-Ann Ann } A)^* = \text{ann ann } A^*$.
- 2) $A_{\#}$ is an ideal of R when $A(1) = 1$ and $(F\text{-Ann Ann } A)_{\#} = \text{ann ann } A_{\#}$.
- 3) $\text{supp } A$ is an ideal of R and $\text{supp } (F\text{-Ann Ann } A) = \text{ann ann } \text{supp } (A)$.

Proof :

To prove (1), since A is an Annihilator fuzzy ideal, then $F\text{-Ann Ann } A = A$

$\Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann Ann } A)^* = A^*$.

But $(F\text{-Ann Ann } A)^* = \{x : x \in R, (F\text{-Ann Ann } A)(x) = (F\text{-Ann Ann } A)(0)\}$.

$\text{ann ann } A^* = \{x : x \in R, ax = 0 \text{ for all } a \in \text{ann } A^*\}$.

$= \{x : x \in R, ax = 0, ab = 0 \text{ for all } b \in A^*\}$.

$= \{x : x \in R, ax = 0, ab = 0, A(b) = A(0)\}$.

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But $A(ab) \geq \max \{A(a), A(b)\} = A(0) = 1$ implies that $A(ab) = 1, A(a) < A(0)$ and $A(ax) = A(0)$.

$$\text{ann ann } A^* = \{x : x \in R, A(ax) = A(0)\}.$$

Since $A(a) < A(0) \Rightarrow A(x) = 1 = A(0)$, then $A^* = \text{ann ann } A^* \Rightarrow A^*$ is annihilator ideal of R .

$$\text{Hence } (F\text{-Ann Ann } A)^* = \text{ann ann } A^*.$$

To prove (2), since A is an Annihilator fuzzy ideal, then $F\text{-Ann Ann } A = A \Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann Ann } A)_\# = A_\#$.

$$\text{But } (F\text{-Ann Ann } A)_\# = \{x : x \in R, (F\text{-Ann Ann } A)(x) > (F\text{-Ann Ann } A)(1)\}.$$

$$\text{ann ann } A_\# = \{x : x \in R, ax = 0 \text{ for all } a \in \text{ann } A_\#\}.$$

$$= \{x : x \in R, ax = 0, ab = 0 \text{ for all } b \in A_\#\}.$$

$$= \{x : x \in R, ax = 0, ab = 0, A(b) > A(1)\}.$$

$$= \{x : x \in R, ax = 0, A(ab) \geq A(b) > A(1)\}.$$

$$= \{x : x \in R, ax = 0, A(ax) = A(0) = 1 \geq A(1)\}.$$

Since $A(1) = 1$, then $\text{ann ann } A_\# = A_\# \Rightarrow A_\#$ is annihilator ideal of R .

$$\text{Hence } (F\text{-Ann Ann } A)_\# = \text{ann ann } A_\#.$$

To prove (3), since A is an Annihilator fuzzy ideal, then $F\text{-Ann Ann } A = A \Rightarrow \text{supp}(F\text{-Ann Ann } A) = \text{supp } A$.

$$\text{But } \text{supp}(F\text{-Ann Ann } A) = \{x : x \in R, (F\text{-Ann Ann } A)(x) > 0\}.$$

$$\text{ann ann } \text{supp}(A) = \{x : x \in R, ax = 0 \text{ for all } a \in \text{ann } \text{supp}(A)\}.$$

$$= \{x : x \in R, ax = 0, ab = 0 \text{ for all } b \in \text{supp}(A)\}.$$

$$= \{x : x \in R, ax = 0, ab = 0 \text{ for all } A(b) > 0\}.$$

$$= \{x : x \in R, A(ax) = 1 > 0\}.$$

$$= \{x : x \in R, A(x) \geq 0\}.$$

$$= \text{supp } A$$

Since $A(x) \neq 0$, then $\text{ann ann } \text{supp}(A) = \text{supp } A \Rightarrow \text{supp } A$ is annihilator ideal of R .

$$\text{Hence } \text{supp}(F\text{-Ann Ann } A) = \text{ann ann } \text{supp}(A).$$

PROPOSITION 3.4 :

Let A and B be two Annihilator fuzzy ideals of a ring R . If $F\text{-Ann } A = F\text{-Ann } B$, then $A = B$.

Proof :

Since $F\text{-Ann Ann } A = A$, and $F\text{-Ann Ann } B = B$.

Suppose that $F\text{-Ann } A=J$, and $F\text{-Ann } B=K$, since $F\text{-Ann } A=F\text{-Ann } B$, then $J=K$ implies that $F\text{-Ann } J= F\text{-Ann } K$, by [9] .

That means $F\text{-Ann } \text{Ann } A=F\text{-Ann } \text{Ann } B$.

Hence $A =B$.

PROPOSITION 3.5 [9] :

Let I be an ideal of a ring R and J be a fuzzy ideal of R which defined by :

$$J(x)=\begin{cases} c & \text{if } x \in I \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

for some $c \in (0,1]$.Then I is an annihilator if and only if J is an Annihilator fuzzy ideal .

PROPOSITION 3.6 :

Let A be an Annihilator fuzzy ideal of a ring R , then $(F\text{-Ann } A)_t = \text{ann } A_t$, $t \in [0,1]$.

Proof :

By definition , $(F\text{-Ann } A)_t = \{x :x \in R, (F\text{-Ann } A)(x) \geq t\}$ and $\text{ann } A_t = \{y :y \in R, yx=0 \text{ for all } x \in A_t \}$.

$$= \{y :y \in R, yx=0 \text{ for all } (A)(x) \geq t \}$$
 .

Let $x \in (F\text{-Ann } A)_t \Rightarrow (F\text{-Ann } A)(x) \geq t = z_t(x)$, $z \in R$, there exists $y \in R$ such that $yx=0$ and $(F\text{-Ann } A)(x) \geq t$, then $(F\text{-Ann } A) \supseteq \langle t \rangle \Rightarrow F\text{-Ann } \langle t \rangle \subseteq F\text{-Ann } \text{Ann } A =A$.

But $(F\text{-Ann } \langle t \rangle)(x) = x_k \circ \langle t \rangle \subseteq \theta_{X(0)} \subseteq A$, $k \in [0,1]$.

Note that : $(F\text{-Ann } \langle t \rangle) = (F\text{-Ann } \langle z_t \rangle)$.

$$\text{Hence } x_k \circ \langle z_t \rangle \subseteq \theta_{X(0)} \subseteq A \Rightarrow (x_k \circ z_t) \subseteq \theta_{X(0)} \subseteq A \Rightarrow$$

$$(x z)_\lambda \subseteq \theta_{X(0)} \subseteq A, \lambda = \min \{k, t\} \Rightarrow \lambda \leq X(0) = 1,$$

(if $\lambda = t \Rightarrow t \leq 1$ or $\lambda = k < t \leq 1 \Rightarrow t \leq 1$), then $\lambda = t$.

Implies that $\{x :x \in R, xz=0, (A)(x) \geq t\} = \text{ann } A_t$.

Hence $(F\text{-Ann } A)_t = \text{ann } A_t$.

PROPOSITION 3.7 :

Let A and B be two Annihilator fuzzy ideals of a ring R , then :

- 1) $(A \cap B)_t = A_t \cap B_t$, $t \in [0,1]$.
- 2) $(A+B)_t = A_t + B_t$, $t \in [0,1]$.
- 3) $[(F\text{-Ann } A)_t + (F\text{-Ann } B)_t] = \text{ann } A_t + \text{ann } B_t$, $t \in [0,1]$.

Proof :

To prove (1) , let $x \in R$,if $x \in (A \cap B)_t \Leftrightarrow (A \cap B)(x) \geq t$.But $(A \cap B)(x) = \min \{A(x) , B(x)\} \geq t \Leftrightarrow A(x) \geq t$ and $(B)(x) \geq t \Leftrightarrow x \in A_t \cap B_t$.

To prove (2), let $x \in R$,if $x \in A_t + B_t \Leftrightarrow x \in A_t , x \in B_t \Leftrightarrow x_t \subseteq A , x_t \subseteq B \Leftrightarrow x_t \subseteq (A + B) \Leftrightarrow$ if $x \in (A+B)_t$.

To prove (3) ,

$[(F-Ann A)_t + (F-Ann B)_t] \subseteq [(F-Ann A) + (F-Ann B)]_t$,by (number 2) .

$\subseteq [F-Ann (A \cap B)]_t$,by proposition (2.4) .

$= \text{ann} (A \cap B)_t$, by proposition (3.6) .

$= \text{ann} (A_t \cap B_t)$, by (number 1) .

$= \text{ann} A_t + \text{ann} B_t$, $t \in [0,1]$,by [11] .

THEOREM 3.1 :

Let I be an ideal of a ring R and A be a fuzzy ideal of R .Then :

$$(F-Ann A)(x) = \begin{cases} A(0) & \text{if } x \in I \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{or } (F-Ann A)(x) = A(0) \text{ for all } x \in R .$$

Proof :

Since $\text{Im}(F-Ann A) \subseteq \{0, A(0)\}$,(proposition (2.6)).

$F-Ann A = \{ x_t : x \in R , x_t \circ A \subseteq 0_t \}$, $t \in [0, A(0)]$.

For any $a \in R$, $(F-Ann A)(a) = \sup \{ t : t \in [0, A(0)] , a_t \circ A \subseteq 0_t \}$.

Let $x \in R$, $(a_t \circ A)(x) = \sup \{ \min \{ a_t(y), A(z) \} \mid x=y, z \}$, $y, z \in R$.

Since $x \in R$,then $x=0$, $x \neq 0$ and $x \in I$, $x \notin I$.

Case (1) If $x=0$,($x \in I$),then :

(a) $a=0$,($0_t \circ A$)(0) = $\sup \{ \min \{ 0_t(y), A(z) \} \mid 0=y, z \}$, $y, z \in R$.

$$= \sup \{ \min \{ 0_t(0), A(0) \}, \min \{ 0_t(0), A(z) \}, \min \{ 0_t(y), A(z) \} \} .$$

$$= \sup \{ \min \{ t, A(0) \}, \min \{ t, A(z) \}, \min \{ 0, A(z) \} \} .$$

$$= \sup \{ t, \min \{ t, A(z) \}, 0 \} .$$

$$= t , \text{ where } t \in \{0, A(0)\} .$$

$$= A(0)$$

(b) $a \neq 0$,($a_t \circ A$)(0) = $\sup \{ \min \{ a_t(y), A(z) \} \mid 0=y, z \}$, $y, z \in R$.

$$= \sup \{ \min \{ t, A(0) \}, \min \{ 0, A(z) \}, \min \{ 0, A(0) \}, \min \{ t, A(z) \} \} .$$

$$= \sup \{ t, \min \{ t, A(z) \}, 0 \} .$$

$$=t, \text{ where } t \in \{0, A(0)\} .$$

$$=A(0)$$

Case (2) If $x \neq 0, (x \in I)$, then :

$$(c) a=0, (0_t \circ A)(x) = \sup \{ \min \{ 0_t(y), A(z) \} \mid x=y, z \}, y, z \in R .$$

$$= \sup \{ \min \{ 0, A(z) \}, \min \{ t, A(z) \} \} .$$

$$=t, \text{ where } t \in \{0, A(0)\} .$$

$$=A(0)$$

(d) $a \neq 0$, that mean $(x \neq 0, a \neq 0, x \in I)$, that there are three possible possibilities :

[(1) $y=a, z=a$, (2) $y=a, z \neq a$, (3) $y \neq a, z=a$]

$$(a_t \circ A)(x) = \sup \{ \min \{ a_t(y), A(z) \} \mid x=y, z \}, y, z \in R .$$

Hence (1) implies that $\min \{ a_t(y), A(z) \} = \min \{ t, A(a) \}$.

(2) implies that $\min \{ a_t(y), A(z) \} = \min \{ t, A(z) \}$.

(3) implies that $\min \{ a_t(y), A(z) \} = \min \{ 0, A(a) \}$.

$$(a_t \circ A)(x) = \sup \{ \min \{ a_t(y), A(z) \} \mid x=y, z \}, y, z \in R .$$

$$= \sup \{ \min \{ t, A(a) \}, \min \{ t, A(z) \}, \min \{ 0, A(a) \} \} .$$

$$= \sup \{ \min \{ t, A(a) \}, \min \{ t, A(z) \}, 0 \} .$$

If $A(a) = A(z) = 0$, hence $(F\text{-Ann } A)(a) = \sup \{ t : t \in [0, A(0)] \}, a_t \circ A \subseteq 0_I = A(0) .$

If $A(a) \neq 0$ or $A(z) \neq 0$, hence $(a_t \circ A)(x) = \sup \{ \min \{ t, A(a) \}, \min \{ t, A(z) \}, 0 \} .$
 $= A(z) = A(0)$ or $A(a) = A(0) .$

Then $(a_t \circ A)(x) = A(0) .$

Case (3) If $x \neq 0, (x \notin I)$, then :

$$(e) a=0, (0_t \circ A)(0) = \sup \{ \min \{ 0_t(y), A(z) \} \mid 0=y, z \}, y, z \in R .$$

$$= \sup \{ \min \{ 0, A(z) \} \} = 0$$

(f) $a \neq 0$, that mean $(x \neq 0, a \neq 0, x \notin I)$, then : $y \neq a, z \neq a .$

implies that $\min \{ a_t(y), A(z) \} = \min \{ 0, A(z) \} = 0 .$

Then $(a_t \circ A)(x) = 0 .$

$$\text{Hence } (F\text{-Ann } A)(x) = \begin{cases} A(0) & \text{if } x \in I \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

If $I = R$, then $(F\text{-Ann } A)(x) = A(0)$ for all $x \in R .$

THEOREM 3.2 :

Let I be an ideal of a ring R and A be a fuzzy ideal of R such that:

$$: A(x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } x \in I \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{where } c \in (0,1], \text{ then } :$$

$$(F - AnnA)(x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } x \in annI \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} .$$

Proof:

$$F-Ann A = \{ x_t : x \in R, x_t \circ A \subseteq 0_1 \}, t \in [0, A(0)] .$$

$$\text{For any } a \in R, (F-Ann A)(a) = \sup \{ t : t \in [0, A(0)], a_t \circ A \subseteq 0_1 \} .$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Since } A(0) = c, (a_t \circ A)(k) &= \sup \{ \min \{ a_t(b), A(d) \} \mid k = b, d \}, k, b, d \in R . \\ &= \sup \{ \min \{ c, c \}, \min \{ 0, c \}, \min \{ c, 0 \}, \min \{ 0, 0 \} \} . \\ &= \min \{ c, c \} = c . \end{aligned}$$

Since $x \in R$, then $x=0, x \neq 0$ and $x \in I, x \notin I$.

If $t=0$, then $F-Ann A = \emptyset$. But that is contradicts .

Since $t \neq 0, a \in F-Ann A$, then:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } x \in I, \text{ then for all } a_s \in I, x_t \circ a_s &= (xa)_\lambda, \lambda = \min \{ t, s \} . \\ &= 0_\lambda \subseteq 0_1 , \end{aligned}$$

then $xa=0$ implies that $x \in ann I$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } x \notin I, \text{ then for all } a_s \in I, x_t \circ a_s &= 0_t \circ a_s = (0a)_\lambda, \lambda = \min \{ t, s \} . \\ &= 0_\lambda \subseteq 0_1 , \end{aligned}$$

implies that $x \notin ann I$.

$$\text{Then } (F - AnnA)(x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } x \in annI \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} .$$

THEOREM 3.3 :

Let I be an ideal of a ring R and A be a fuzzy ideal of R . If A is an Annihilator fuzzy ideal

$$\text{, then } A \text{ is defined by } : A(x) = \begin{cases} A(0) & \text{if } x \in I \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{or } A(x) = A(0) \text{ for all } x \in R .$$

Proof:

Since $A(0) \neq 0$, then A is nonempty fuzzy ideal of R .

A is Annihilator fuzzy ideal, then $| \text{Im}(A) | \leq 2$, by [proposition (3.1)] .

That mean $\text{Im } A \subseteq \{0, A(0)\}$, and $\text{Im}(F-Ann A) \subseteq \{0, A(0)\}$, by [proposition (2.6) and proposition (3.1)],

and $(F - AnnA)(x) = \begin{cases} A(0) & \text{if } x \in annI \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$, by Theorem (3.2) or $F-Ann A(x) = A(0)$ by

Theorem (3.1).

But $F-Ann A$ is a fuzzy ideal of R , by [proposition (2.1)], then

$(F - AnnAnnA)(x) = \begin{cases} A(0) & \text{if } x \in annannI \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$, by Theorem (3.2) or $F-Ann Ann A(x)$

$= A(0)$ by Theorem (3.1).

But A is Annihilator fuzzy ideal, that mean $F-Ann Ann A = A$, implies that

$A(x) = \begin{cases} A(0) & \text{if } x \in I \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$, or $A(x) = A(0)$ for all $x \in R$.

COROLLARY 3.1 :

Let I be an ideal of a ring R and A be a fuzzy ideal of R . If A is an Annihilator fuzzy ideal

which defined by : $A(x) = \begin{cases} A(0) & \text{if } x \in I \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$, then I is an annihilator ideal of R .

Proof :

It is clear by [Theorem (3.3) and proposition (3.3)].

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On Annihilator Fuzzy Ideals 2

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حول المثاليات الضبابية التالفة 2

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المستخلص

ومنذ ذلك الحين (fuzzy sets) مفهوم المجموعات الضبابية (Zadeh L.A.) في عام 1965, أُجريت العديد من البحوث في مختلف المجالات الرياضية النظرية والتطبيقية حول هذا الموضوع. وفي عام 1982 صاغ ليو (Liu W.J.) مصطلح الحلقة الضبابية (fuzzy ring) وعَرَّفها وعَرَّف كذلك مفهوم المثالي الضبابي (fuzzy ideal). وفي عام 2000 عرف حميد (Hameed A.T) مصطلح المثالي الضبابي التالفي (Annihilator fuzzy Ideal) وبين بعض الخواص المتعلقة بها. في هذا البحث استخدمنا مفهوم المثاليات الضبابية التالفة كتعميم للمثاليات التالفة الاعتيادية وأوضحنا بعض الخواص الأساسية والمبرهنات حول هذا الموضوع.